

Understanding the nature of Career Planning among the Higher Secondary students in Coimbatore and Tirupur District

R. Selvapranambika

PG Diploma in Career Guidance for Executives
Dept. of Extension and Career Guidance, Bharathiar University
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

Prof. Dr. A. Vimala

Head, Dept. of Extension and Career Guidance
Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

Abstract

Purpose of the Research: Career guidance in young children is most important, since higher secondary students unable to prepare for their next level in their career. Students studying at higher secondary school not getting any regular support in terms of career guidance and counseling from school or government. The current research aims at finding the factors affecting the career planning of higher secondary students. The results found that majority of the students didn't plan earlier because they opined that they were not properly educated and counseled with any career guidance programme in the school level. **Methodology:** This study is a descriptive and exploratory in nature and includes oral interview method and questionnaire as tools for data collection. **Findings:** From the findings and discussion, the major result found that, among the respondents of government and private school, 60.7% of them were not received any career guidance in school level and 90% of them were opined they are in need of career guidance in the school level. **Implications:** This would bring long-term benefits in terms of systemic changes amongst students in improving career choices. It would also help the government to formulate policy and implementation for bringing structural changes in the system. **Originality:** This study succeed in finding the understanding of career development among government and private school

Key words: Career planning, Career choice, Factors affecting career planning and career awareness

Introduction

According to Ginzberg career development theory at the age of 11-17 years they will be in tentative stage, kids start to become aware of their surroundings. In this stage, they will start developing their skills, abilities, and talents. Apart from that, they are characterized by their interests and values. Students will be able to plan their own career and they have choice after accessing their interest, capacity, value and various career options with the help of career counselors or guide from schools, teachers, elders from family and relatives. Career Planning is characterised the procedure, through which students comes to settle on profession related choices. In late adulthood and early adult ages, career planning becomes a significant role in choosing career for their life because higher secondary school students enter a period in their life looking for career information and becoming aware of vocal interest. Many factors influence the career planning of students like Parents occupation, Economical factors, Parents suggestion, Social factors, Peer pressure etc

According to the article from Mindler in 2019, India is in massive shortage of career counsellor, In comparison, U.S. has about 2.6 million student career advisors for 56 million students career guidance and mentoring is only now beginning to gain the recognition it deserves and is witnessing exponential growth as a profession. While the developed nations have recognized the criticality of career counselling, and a vast number of progressive schools in India are also waking up to the fact, the scenario is more sober in reality. Over 90% of Indian schools do not have career counsellors and there is a massive shortage of trained career counsellors in the country today.

Literature support

According to Musbashir Zafar Study (2019) evidence that those who take counseling for career choosing have reduction the difficulty for career decision making process. Information regarding career guidance has prime importance for career decision making process. There are several recommendations for career counseling and guidance in the view to study results, first using the CDDQ(Career Decision making difficulty questionnaire)in career guidance counselor

are effective tool for career decision making and encouraged the using this tool. The study should be replicated in future in large scale for explore the determinants of career counseling specifically in adolescent age which is prime age group for career decision making

According to the study of Mark.A.McKnight (2009) from University of Southern Indiana USA, his study concluded that students from regional high schools and vocational/technical schools and programs have insufficient access to career exploration activities, especially at an early age. Because of this insufficient access, these students begin career planning at late stages, many times as late as their final year of high school, and are frequently not able to name a specific occupation they will pursue.

According to the Assessor's Perspective in Ghaninan case (2015) school counsellors play significant role in the total development of students in respect to career choices. Results from the study showed that students strongly agreed that career guidance and counseling, career goal identification, organization of career days and conferences, administration of occupational interest inventory on students were among career intervention roles by the school counsellor influence their choice of career. Further, there was a positive correlation between the role of the counsellor and its influence on student's choice of career. It is thus recommended that frequent intervention programmers need to be provided to support students make well informed choices

According to Ramalatha Marimuthu (2019), the paper describes the necessity for early introduction of career guidance program in the schools. Choice of education is greatly influenced by economic need and creating jobs in all sectors balances the supply and demand and prevents the drainage of human resources in one sector leaving the other sectors with lack of human resources. The schools play an important role in bringing this knowledge to the students and developing their motivation to their aspirations and interests balancing the economic requirements.

Research methodology

This study is a descriptive and exploratory in nature and includes oral interview method and questionnaire as tools for data collection. The research was carried out in students of Higher Secondary Schools in Dindigul and Tiruppur districts of Tamil Nadu. Two types of sample were selected for the data collection. A structured questionnaire was administered among the sample respondent of 82 students to know their nature of career planning. An oral interview was conducted among the sample of 40 school students to know the effectiveness of career guidance and they were undergone three days career awareness programme was offered by the qualified career counselor. The secondary data were collected from the various journals, articles, newspapers, books, and websites. Frequency analysis was adopted for the framed objective for analysis and interpretations. Interpretations were done through collected and tabulated data.

Research objective

This research article focus on the following objectives to understand the higher secondary students career planning and the causative factors

- To access the demographic profile among the students of higher secondary school
- To understand the factors affecting career planning among the students of higher secondary school
- To find the career choice among the government and private students of higher secondary school
- To find the career awareness and career effectiveness among higher secondary school students after the career counselling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The collected data has been tabulated and analyzed with applying necessary statistical tool to arrive the result for the framed objectives.

Parent's education of government and private school students

The result found that, 46.4% of parents were 10th qualified and same represented as illiterate in the government school and 45.2% of parents were 12th qualified in private school. The above results are supported by the past research of Owerri (2016) Miracle Ifeoma Mbagwu and et al shows that parents educational background influences teenagers career choice, it has also revealed that teenagers whose parents are from high educational background are more consistent and do not have much difficulties in making career choice when compared with those whose parents have low educational background.

Parent's occupation of government and private school students

Regarding the respondent's parent occupation, 75% of parents working as a daily wages in government school students and only 43.3% of parents were doing business among the respondents of private school. This also compared with the early study of Arulmani.G and et al in (2003) career decision making self-efficacy scores of students whose parents had full time employment was significantly higher than the students whose parents were unemployed or part time jobs.

Career Choice of government and private school students

Career choice among the respondents showed that on an average of 39.75% of students interested to take any arts and science field who is studying at government and in Private school.

Factors affecting the growth of career development

Among the respondents, the result found that 45.1 % of students were opined that the financial crisis is the most important factors, which is affecting the career decisions. This is evident that an Indian family from a lower socio-economic status (SES) background tends to lay a lower emphasis on investing resources in education as a pathway to a career when compared to Indian middle- class groups (Arulmani 2011).

Career awareness among school students

Regarding the career guidance, that 75.8% of the respondents have not received any career guidance opined by government school students. On an average, 60.7% of students from both government and private school have not received any career guidance.

Awareness of various courses after twelfth grade

72% of the student was familiar on regular and conventional courses and not familiar on various new emerging courses and the vocational courses such as forensic Cyber security,
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Paramedical and defense related courses. Also, 64% of the students from government schools were not familiar on various common entrance examinations for the admission of UG programme in the state and central universities.

Need and understanding the effectiveness of career guidance

Among the respondents, 90% of the students were mentioned that they need career guidance in school level for next level career planning. This is supported by mindler, over 90% of Indian schools do not have career counsellors and there is a massive shortage of trained career counsellors in the country. After the formal career guidance training for the respondents, 82.5% of them were opined that, the given career guidance will help them for career planning effectively. 62.5% came to know about the new courses available in the state and central after formal career guidance. 72.5% mentioned they need continuous career guidance in schools and colleges for the preparation of job opportunities.

Recommendations

From the findings and discussion, the major result found that, among the respondents of government and private school, 60.7% of them were not received any career guidance in school level and 90% of them were opined they are in need of career guidance in the school level. In the above circumstances, it is recommended that

- Need of establishment of career guidance cell in schools and the higher education institutions are alone an effective solution.
- The schools and colleges has to organize a career fair at least two times in a year to the students, which will make them students familiar on various courses and job opportunities for their next level career preparation.
- Capacity building program on career guidance to be offered to the school teachers to serve them to certain extent on student guidance.
- Parents meetings need to be arranged in the schools to create the awareness of various courses and job facilities available.
- Appointment of professional and qualified career guide in schools and colleges will offer the right career guidance to the young minds for their right choice.

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